

The Impact of Paternalistic Leadership on Job Attitudes A Study on Sadat City University in Egypt

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Abstract

The objective of the research is to identify the impact of Paternalistic Leadership (PL) on Job Attitudes (JA) in terms of Job Satisfaction (JS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) at Sadat City University (SCU) in Egypt. About 400 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 75%.

The research discovered a number of results: (1) PL has an impact on JA in terms of JS and OC. (2) The first hypothesis of the paper looked for the significance of the relationship between PL and JS. The research showed that there was a significant relationship between TL and JS (3) The second hypothesis looked for finding whether PL has significant capacity to influence OC. The research showed that there was a significant relationship between PL and OC. (4) There are three dimensions of PL which are benevolent leadership, moral leadership and authoritarian Leadership. These dimensions have a significant impact on JS and OC (5) The current research has shown that the dimensions of Paternalistic Leadership (benevolent leadership, moral leadership, and authoritarian leadership) play an important role in influencing the job attitudes of employees (6) SCU suffers from the widespread phenomenon of the leader's adherence to work-related information and not disclosing it to subordinates (7) The leader at SCU cares about the subordinates and takes care of the amount of work they do (8) The current research indicates that benevolent leadership ranked first, moral leadership came in second place, and authoritarian leadership came in third place. (9) The leader of the SCU is credible and honest. (10) The leader of SCU does not provide assistance to those who are absent from work or make recommendations for the development of the university

The study referred to a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: (1) Leaders at SCU should engage subordinates in decision-making and allow them to express their opinions and suggestions. (2) Leaders in SCU should follow a differentiated behavior that is appropriate to each circumstance or situation to minimize or reduce the deviant behavior. (3) Leaders should exert pressure on subordinates at SCU. (4) Leaders should strive to develop a set of regulations and laws that determine the competencies and powers of managers and staff at SCU. (5) Leaders should make employees identical with SCU by adopting different means including generating a sense of being part of the university and involving it in decision-making. (6) Leaders at SCU should do more to improve positive staff behaviors and reduce deviant behaviors. (7) Leaders should strive to provide the principle of democracy in dealing with employees at SCU with the necessity of ethical aspects when dealing with subordinates. (8) Leaders at SCU should put restrictions on the practice of negative behaviors by activating a strict control system as well as applying strict rules towards those who do these behaviors. (9) Leaders at SCU should increase the awareness of individuals of the importance of the role they play, through the freedom to express their views and suggestions. (10) Leaders should provide justice among workers, in procedures, distribution and dealings at SCU in Egypt.

Keywords: *Paternalistic Leadership, Job Attitudes*

1. Introduction

Paternalistic Leadership is one of the most common leadership styles in Chinese culture, known as Chinese paternalistic leadership as an alternative to transformational leadership (Mu et al., 2012).

The patriarchal leader is characterized by a wise role in exercising his powers with his subordinates, for possessing a philosophy of persuasion as well as avoiding unethical behaviors within the work so that he can attract the trust of his subordinates (Sheer, 2012).

Paternalistic Leadership greatly affects employee performance through a range of functional behaviors. Several previous studies have found direct relationships between paternalistic leadership and many organizational variables such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, loyalty, and organizational citizenship behaviors (Chen et al., 2012).

There is no agreement among researchers on the concept of paternalistic leadership, but most of them agreed that paternalistic leadership could be described as a type of leadership. In paternalistic leadership, the leader is assumed to have a function such as that of the head of the household and his task begins to improve his relations with members of his community by maintaining them (Chukwudi, 2009).

Although there is disagreement among researchers on the definition of the concept of paternalistic leadership, the majority of these researchers agreed that paternalistic leadership has three main dimensions: authoritarian leadership, benevolent leadership, and moral leadership (Cicellin, et al., 2015; Chou, 2015).

Authoritarian leadership refers to the conduct of a leader who has full authority and control over subordinates and demands subordinates to complete obedience (Ozcelik & Cenkci, 2014).

Benevolent Leadership means having good relationships with employees and working to create a friendly working environment, which benefits the organization (Anwar, 2013).

Moral Leadership refers to leadership that respects the rights and dignity of others and has four main dimensions: integrity, altruism, collective motivation, and collective encouragement (Resick et al., 2006).

Job Satisfaction (JS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) are key job attitudes (George & Jones, 1997; Jehn et al., 1999; MacKenzie et al., 1998).

OC and JS differ mainly in the following (1) OC can be defined as the emotional responses that an employee has towards his organization; and (2) JS is the responses that an employee has towards any job. These two variables are highly interrelated as an employee may have positive feelings towards the organization, its values and objectives, but he may be unsatisfied with his job at the organization (Meyer et al., 2002).

OC and JS are interrelated; they have diverse attitudes. OC is the better means of constancy, belonging and permanence compared to JS (Lane et al., 2010).

This article aims to have a literature review of PL and JA. It proposes a conceptual model that addresses the relationship between PL, JS and OC SCU in Egypt. In other words, it discusses PL, JS and OC in order to highlight the results of previous studies. Based on these findings, it proposes a conceptual framework. Also, it concludes the importance of PL at SCU in Egypt.

This article is organized as follows (1) introduction, (2) literature review, (3) research model, (4) research questions and hypotheses, (5) the research strategy, (6) empirical results, (7) the research findings, (8) the research recommendations, and (9) future research

2. Literature Review

2.1. Paternalistic Leadership

2.1.1. Paternalistic Leadership Concept

There are diversified views on the concept of Paternalistic Leadership. This is due to the ambiguity of this concept (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008).

Paternalistic Leadership is a leadership style that resembles the role of the father in the family. It combines strong power with concern for subordinates and consideration. In other words, it is the pattern that takes care of workers. A leader in Paternalistic Leadership cares for and protects subordinates and carries them with respect and appreciation (Hakimian et al., 2014).

Paternalistic Leadership means the leadership of the family as the father who uses his power to promote the well-being of the family, and it combines goodness with patriarchal domination (Humphreys et al., 2014).

Paternalistic Leadership is a pattern that encompasses strict discipline and authority, patriarchal charity, and moral integrity in the prevailing climate of the organization (Chen, 2013).

Paternalistic Leadership means that the leader behaves like the father with the children and is keen to help employees and solve their personal problems in every way possible, and as a result of this attention will be the loyalty of the subordinates to the leader and the organization (Anwar, 2013).

Paternalistic Leadership is a subordinate relationship between the leader and the subordinate, in which the leader exercises his or her personal and professional life in a manner similar to the father in the family, and in return expects them to be loyal and respectful (Balassiano et al., 2012).

Paternalistic Leadership consists of morality, benevolence and domination. Morality refers to personal virtues, self-discipline and generosity. Charity refers to the concern for the personal and family well-being of subordinates. Authoritarianism indicates that the leader exercises absolute authority and demands unquestioned obedience (Wu et al., 2012).

Paternalistic Leadership combines patriarchal authority and charity, strong discipline, and moral integrity (Wu & Tsai, 2012).

Paternalistic Leadership is one of the methods of trusted leadership, which is characterized by the charity as the father and the moral integrity of the leader within his authority (Hsieh & Chen, 2011).

Paternalistic Leadership is a hierarchical relationship in which a leader directs the professional and personal life of subordinates in a manner similar to the treatment of parents. Conversely, loyalty and respect

are expected from subordinates (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2010).

Paternalistic Leadership is a hierarchical relationship, in which the leader directs his subordinates both in their professional and personal lives. Loyalty and respect on their part are expected. In other words, it is a subordinate relationship in which the leader exercises his personal and professional life for subordinates in a manner similar to the father in the family, and in return expects loyalty and respect (Gelfand et al., 2007).

Paternalistic Leadership is managing people in a framework of patriarchal charity, prestige, impartiality and altruism. In other words, it is a combination of power, charity, and moral integrity (Cheng et al., 2004).

2.1.2. Paternalistic Leadership Dimensions

The dimensions of Paternalistic Leadership are benevolent, moral, and authoritarian, (Cicellin, et al., 2015; Chou, 2015; Rajasekar & Beh, 2013; Kai, 2013; Wu et al., 2012; Wu, et al, 2011; Hou-ming & Bo, 2011; Niu, et al, 2009; Cheng, et al., 2004; Farh & Cheng, 2000). These dimensions can be illustrated as follows:

2.1.2.1. Benevolent Leadership

Benevolent Leadership is the process of creating a positive circle of encouragement and implementing positive change in organizations through (1) taking ethical decisions and actions, (2) developing spiritual awareness in the community, (3) hope and courage to promote positive action, (4) leaving a positive impact in Society (Tan, 2015).

Benevolent Leadership is a concern for the subordinate personal and family well-being. Benevolent Leadership provides individual care and privileges, tolerates subordinates, maintains a family-friendly work environment and promotes informal personal relationships with subordinates (Rajasekar & Beh, 2013).

Benevolent Leadership means having good relationships with employees and working to create a friendly work environment, which benefits the organization (Anwar, 2013).

Benevolent Leadership suggests that leaders must use goodness with subordinates, and that subordinates in turn must give loyalty and gratitude to their leaders (Tsia, 2012).

Benevolent Leadership takes care of subordinates and encourages them to find solutions when faced with specific problems (Rehman & Afsar, 2012).

Benevolent Leadership achieves the common interest or positive results of all or most members of society (Karakas & Emine, 2011).

Benevolent Leadership is divided into two parts; either individually or collectively for subordinates (Min et al., 2011).

Benevolent Leadership focuses on achieving perceived benefits, or results for the common good (Karakas, 2009).

2.1.2.2. Moral Leadership

Research on moral leadership has proliferated since the mid-1990s, and moral leadership is characterized by a high degree of personal integrity (Hu et al, 2015).

Moral leadership takes care of subordinates and cares for them in areas that are outside the scope of official work, and concerns the material and psychological needs of followers. Interest also extends to the family of subordinates. The relationship between the leader and the subordinate is in the long run, and that dealing with subordinates is respectful (Farh, 2014).

Moral leadership is a leading role in individual and ethical behavior; this requires leaders to have a high level of self-discipline and moral integrity (Kai, 2013).

Moral Leadership means the leader's personality with integrity and moral awareness that encourages team development and preference for organizational interests over personal interests. A moral leader plays an important role in influencing subordinates and their behaviors, so a leader who wants to achieve the goals of his organization must have good morals to gain others and the ability to achieve goals (Resick et al., 2011).

Moral leadership means doing the right thing with others and it is essential in society with different customs and traditions (Zimmerli, et al, 2007).

There are three dimensions of moral leadership: (1) the legitimate dimension of moral leadership is that moral leadership seeks to clarify the normative principles that apply to the relationship between the employer, subordinates and the manager, (2) the organizational dimension of moral leadership is that leadership is within organizational frameworks, and that ethical leadership includes implications for the ethical standards of culture in organizations, and (3) the individual dimension of moral leadership is that moral leadership defines virtues and serves the moral development of individual business leaders (Becker, 2007).

Moral leadership refers to leadership that respects the rights and dignity of others. It has four main dimensions: integrity, altruism, collective motivation, and collective encouragement (Resick et al., 2006).

Moral leadership is the extent to which administrative leaders can demonstrate appropriate ethical behaviors through personal actions and relationships, and encourage subordinates to do so (Brown et al., 2005).

2.1.2.3. Authoritarian Leadership

Authoritarian leadership is the practice of controlling subordinates, and they deliberately ignore the suggestions and contributions of subordinates (Liu & Wang, 2015).

Authoritarian leadership refers to the behavior of a leader who has full authority and control over subordinates and demands subordinates to complete obedience (Ozcelik & Cenkci, 2014).

Authoritarian leadership negatively affects subordinates' attitudes and behaviors, such as employee satisfaction with their leaders, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior (Zhang et al, 2014).

Authoritarian leadership indicates that a leader does not respect others in making decisions, as well as a leader's behaviors that emphasize absolute authority and control that requires obedience (Mussolino & Calabro, 2013).

Authoritarian leadership is that the leader is strong in his authority, has absolute authority, has strict control over subordinates, and must obey fully without reservation (Fu et al., 2013).

Autocratic leadership is less concerned with the needs of subordinates, and disciplinary measures are often used to control individual behaviors (Carr, 2013).

Authoritarian leadership focuses on absolute power, controlling subordinates and making them feel uncomfortable, and there is tension in the interrelationships between supervisors and subordinates (Wu et al., 2012).

Authoritarian leadership refers to the conduct of a leader who emphasizes absolute authority and control over subordinates and asks them to obey without any discussion (Wu, et al, 2011).

Authoritarian leadership emphasizes not only individual authority and subordinate hegemony but also contains different types of behavior such as authoritarianism, subversion, etc. (Min et al, 2011).

Autocratic leadership is interested in making decisions without the participation of subordinates, and this leads to a cumbersome atmosphere characterized by complaints and blaming others. The level of power varies from one command pattern to another, as the authoritarian leader uses the method of sanctions against subordinates (Moskovich, 2009).

Authoritarian leadership refers to the conduct of a leader who emphasizes absolute authority and control over subordinates and demands them to be fully obedient (Cheng, et al., 2004).

2.2. Job Attitudes

Two important aspects of Job Attitudes are Organizational Commitment (OC) and Job Satisfaction (JS) for the employees in the organizations (Dewettinck & Van Amejide, 2011).

2.2.1. Job Satisfaction

JS is important that its absence often leads to lethargy and reduced OC. Dissatisfied employees are more likely to quit their jobs or be absent than satisfied employees (Ilhami & Bektas 2012).

JS relates to an individual's perceptions of a job, and this perception is in turn influenced by their circumstances, including needs, values and expectations (Sheykhshabani & Beshlideh, 2011).

JS is the amount of pleasure an employee has with the job and it can differ from employee to another (Farsi, et al., 2010).

JS is one of the most frequently measured organizational variables in both research and applied settings and that has been widely studied in organizational behavior and organizational psychology (Eric et al., 2010).

JS is explained as the feelings a worker has about his or her job experiences related to previous experiences, current expectations, or available alternatives (Zarea, et al., 2009).

JS draws on the nature of the job, besides the expectation of an employee from the job (Hussami, 2008).

JS impacts both individuals and organizations. On the individual level, JS impacts stress (Zeytinoglu et al. 2007; Lambert, et al., 2007), and burnout (Oncel, et al., 2007). On the organizational level, however, JS impacts empowerment (Hechanova, et al., 2006), customer satisfaction (Homburg & Stock, 2004), service quality and performance (Park & Deitz, 2006), and OC (Al-Ajmi, 2006).

JS is the degree of congruence between the characteristics of a job and the employee's perceived qualities. It is the extent that the working environment meets the needs and values of employees and the individual's response to that environment (Tewksbury & Higgins, 2006).

JS is a global construct or a constellation of different dimensions to which the employee reacts affectively. It can be understood as the way employees feel about their jobs and different aspects of their jobs. JS is a positive emotional reaction to a particular job. It is not a unitary concept. An employee can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of the job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2006).

JS means personal gratification from one's work, pleasure and feeling of accomplishment employees derive from performing their jobs (Elbert & Griffin, 2005).

JS is of interest to workers in organizations and those studying them. It is a salient variable in organizational behavior research, as well as the theory of organizational experience ranging from job design to supervision (Hong et al., 2005).

JS is a sign of organizational effectiveness as most employers realize that the optimal functioning of their organization depends on JS (Saari & Judge, 2004).

There are two dimensions of JS. They are internal satisfaction and external satisfaction (Judge et al., 2001; Best & Thurston, 2004):

- **Internal Satisfaction:** this means the opportunities to demonstrate abilities, sense of achievement obtained from work, ethical values of the work, opportunities to provide services.
- **External Satisfaction:** this means job content, salary, unobstructed channels for promotion, work environment and equipment.

2.2.2. Organizational Commitment

OC looks like a strong magnetic force attracting one metallic object to another. It indicates the degree to which an employee identifies with the organization and wants to remain within the organization in the future (Awad & Alhashemi, 2012).

OC widely is described as a key factor in the relationship between individuals and organizations (Sharma & Bajpai, 2010).

OC is an individual's willingness to dedicate efforts and loyalty to an organization (Jalonen, et al., 2006; Wagner, 2007). OC is important because committed employees are likely to be more willing to make personal sacrifices for the sake of the organization (Vitell, & Singhapakdi, 2007).

The employee who is highly committed to the organization contributes to the organization's performance. Because it is linked with absenteeism, work effort and turnover OC is very important (Joiner & Bakalis, 2006).

OC reflects the work attitudes of employees toward the organizations in which they work (Silverthorne, 2004).

OC is very beneficial for the organization as it reduces the absenteeism rate and turns over and enhancing the organization's productivity (Jernigan et al., 2002).

OC can be classified into three categories. They are affective, continuance and normative. Each category is related to the other and they represent employee's relationships with organizations. All of the types of commitment have implications for the decision to continue or discontinue membership of the organization (Meyer et al, 2002).

OC refers to employees' feelings and levels of attachment to their organizations. If an employee desires to remain in an organization, exerts effort willingly, believes in and accepts to organization's values and goals, OC can be enhanced in an organization (Barlett, 2001).

In this study, we follow Meyer and Allen (1991) three dimensions of OC (affective, continuous, and normative):

1. **Affective Commitment (AC):** It is influenced by the degree to which the individual perceives the characteristics of his work from the degree of independence of work and skills required and the proximity of supervisors and guidance to them. Also, it is affected by the extent of the individual's sense that the organizational environment to which he belongs allows him to participate in decision-making within the organization. AC refers to an employee's continuing to work for an organization thanks to emotional attachment to, involvement in, and identification with that organization (Rashid et al., 2003).
2. **Continuous Commitment (CC):** It is the strength of an individual's desire to keep currency in the organization because he believes that leaving the job costs him a lot. In other words, CC is the integration of the individual into the activities of the organization, taking into account the costs that the individual will bear if he leaves the organization. CC refers to the commitment based on the costs that are associated with leaving a specific organization. CC refers to the commission based on the costs that are associated with leaving a specific organization (Greenberg & Baron, 2003).
3. **Normative Commitment (NC):** It refers to the individual's sense of the obligation to remain in the organization because he does not wish to harm the interests of the organization and to leave a bad impression on his colleagues. In other words, NC is the literary sense of the need for survival in the organization. NC relates to feelings of obligation to remain with the organization, i.e. employee with a strong sense of normative commitment remain in organizations because they feel they ought to do so. NC relates to feelings of obligation to remain with the organization, i.e. employee with a strong sense of normative commitment remain in organizations because they feel they ought to do so (Ayeni & Phopoola, 2007, Omar, et al. 2008).

3. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable for the study of PL. There is one dependent variable JA.

Figure (1): The Research Model

The research framework suggests that PL has an impact on JA (JS and OC) at SCU in Egypt.

The present study handles PL as an independent variable. PL is measured in terms of benevolent leadership, moral leadership, and authoritarian leadership. It is worthy of mention that this measure consists of 15 statements (Rajasekar & Beh, 2013; Kai, 2013; Fu, et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2012; Cheng, 2009).

The present study handles JS as a dependent variable. JS is measured in terms of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction. It is worthy of mentioning that this measure consists of 10 statements (Judge et al., 2001; and Best & Thurston, 2004).

The present study handles OC as a dependent variable. OC is measured in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment). It is worthy of mentioning that this measure consists of 18 statements (Allan & Meyer, 1990; Meyer, et. al., 1993).

4. Research Questions

Paternalistic Leadership has positive effects on society at large because of the ability to have the emotional trust of subordinates. Emotional confidence demonstrates personal ties and positive feelings towards the leader and plays an important role in explaining how a patriarchal leader can motivate his followers to meet high performance standards (Chen 2011).

Paternalistic Leadership provides care and guidance to subordinates in their professional and personal lives in a paternalistic manner and in return expects loyalty and respect from employees (Aycaan et al., 2013).

Paternalistic Leadership affects individual, group, and organizational outcomes in organizations, and a potential outcome of parental leadership is increased work flexibility, reduced turnover and improved commitment, loyalty and teamwork (Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014).

The researcher reached the research problem through two sources. The first is the previous studies that dealt with the relationship between PL and JA. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment in general and SCU in particular. The second is the pilot study which was conducted with 30 employees at SCU to identify the dimensions of PL and JA. The researcher found several indicators that explain the importance of PL in influencing JA at SCU. The research questions are as follows:

Q1: What is the statistical relationship between PL (Benevolent Leadership) and JS at SCU.

Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between PL (Moral Leadership) and JS at SCU?

Q3: What is the statistical relationship between PL (Authoritarian Leadership) and JS at SCU.

Q4: What is the statistical relationship between PL (Benevolent Leadership) and OC at SCU.

Q5: What is the nature of the relationship between PL (Moral Leadership) and OC at SCU?

Q6: What is the statistical relationship between PL (Authoritarian Leadership) and OC at SCU.

5. Research Hypotheses

The results of many previous studies confirm the relationship between PL and some other variables, not including JS, where one of the studies was concerned with the analysis of the relationship between PL and the creative behavior of employees. The results of this study indicated that there a statistically significant relationship between PL and the creative behavior of workers. It was also found that job insecurity as an intermediate variable has a significant negative impact on the relationship between PL and the creative behavior of employees (Hakimian et al., 2014).

There are numerous studies in Paternalistic Leadership that has focused on strengthening the role of subordinates in the organization. These studies have shown that Paternalistic Leadership significantly influenced the performance and effectiveness of subordinates and organizational outputs, including loyalty to the leader, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior and job performance (Cheng & Wang, 2014).

In a comprehensive study of a wide range of employees in small Chinese family businesses to demonstrate the three dimensions of PL (benevolent leadership, moral leadership, and authoritarian leadership) in those companies and determining the viewpoints of employees. The majority of views were positive with high competitive correlations between those dimensions of PL (Sheer, 2012).

There have been many previous studies on the relationship between PL and JS. A study has shown that benevolent leadership has a positive impact on JS. On the other hand, the authoritarian leadership has a positive impact on the motivation level of employees at work. Also, moral leadership has no negative or positive impact on employee results. Finally, the study found that PL has a positive impact on employee outcomes (Anwar, 2013).

JS depends on the bonding between the leader and employees. This bond will tell whether employees are satisfied or dissatisfied. The work environment also plays an important role in the JS level of the employees. Leaders who will have a strong relationship with his/her employees will have a more motivated workforce and the employees JS level will be at its highest level (Chen & Silverthorne, 2005; Madlock, 2008).

Transformational leaders tend to encourage and motivate their followers to take on more responsibility and autonomy thereby enhancing employees' sense of accomplishment and JS (Emery & Barker, 2007).

Leadership styles are found to correlate positively with employee perceptions of job, leader and JS (Felfe & Schyns, 2006).

Leadership style plays a vital role in influencing employees' JS. Some researchers discovered that different leadership styles would engender a different working environment and directly affect the JS (Timothy & Ronald, 2004).

Situation Leadership Theory (SLT) has emphasized the relationship between leadership and job performance, little research has been undertaken in this area (Avery & Ryan, 2002).

Leadership styles relate to different levels of JS. When leaders demonstrated high levels of consideration and supportive behavior, their subordinates tended to have a higher level of JS (Packard & Kauppi (1999).

The relationship between leadership style and JS in different organizations has been studied extensively. A human-oriented leadership style increases JS. Leaders sometimes have a strong influence on employee and organizational outcomes (Vries et al., 1998).

Many studies have found leadership styles involved in relationship-oriented behavior have a positive relationship with JS and performance (Wilkinson & Wagner, 1993).

Employees are most satisfied when they perceive their supervisors as exhibiting both relational and task-oriented behaviors (Castaneda & Nahavandi, 1991). Transactional and transformational leadership have been widely linked to positive individual and organizational consequences (Bass, 1990).

There are several studies that have demonstrated that participative decision-making can be beneficial to workers' mental health and JS (Fisher, 1989). Leadership behaviors affect outcomes, such as group performance and goal attainment, by influencing the behaviors of subordinates (Vroom & Jago, 1988).

Transformational leadership might intrinsically foster more JS, given its ability to impart a sense of mission and intellectual stimulation (Bass, 1985).

Accordingly, the first hypothesis of the study can be formulated in the form of imposition of nothingness as follows:

H1: There is no statistically significant relationship between PL (benevolent leadership) and JS at SCU in Egypt.

H2: PL (moral leadership) of employees has no statistically significant effect on JS at SCU in Egypt.

H3: There is no relationship between PL (authoritarian leadership) and JS at SCU in Egypt.

The results of many previous studies confirm the relationship between PL and some other variables, not including OC, where one of the studies was concerned with the analysis of the relationship between PL and employee performance. The results of this study indicated that there is a positive correlation, between benevolent leadership and moral leadership with employee performance, as well as a negative correlation between authoritarian leadership and employee performance (Chen et al., 2011).

Another study aimed to explore the relationship between the three dimensions of patriarchal leadership (benevolent leadership, moral leadership, and authoritarian leadership) and the ethical climate. The findings show that PL has beneficial effects on the ethical climate that will guide efforts to strengthen training and organizational programs, or promotional activities for subsequent leaders (Riveros & Tsia, 2011).

There have been many previous studies on the relationship between PL and OC. A study has shown that benevolent leadership has a significant effect on OC. Also, the authoritarian leadership has a positive impact on the employee's motivation. Furthermore, moral leadership has no negative or positive on employee outcomes. Finally, the study found that PL has a positive impact on employee outcomes (Anwar, 2013).

There have been many previous studies on the relationship between OC and JS. A study indicated the impact of OC on JS. The results of this study resulted in a positive relationship between OC and JS, as well

as between employee performance and JS (Ahmad et al., 2014). Findings in another study indicate that levels of age do not lead to increases or decreases in OC. There is no significant relationship between functional background and OC. Females and males behave equally in terms of OC (Kargar, 2012).

The results of another study showed a statistically significant and positive effect between work motivation, JS and OC. The impact of JS on OC is also relatively stronger than that of business motivation on OC (Warsi et al., 2009). Accordingly, the second hypothesis of the study can be formulated in the form of imposition of nothingness as follows:

H4: There is no statistically significant relationship between PL (benevolent leadership) and OC at SCU in Egypt.

H5: PL (moral leadership) of employees has no statistically significant effect on OC at SCU in Egypt.

H6: There is no relationship between PL (authoritarian leadership) and OC at SCU in Egypt.

6. Research Population

The total population at SCU in Egypt is 801 employees. Due to the small number of the research community, it was decided to use complete numeration or census. The research population is illustrated in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Faculty Members	Number	Percentage
1. Faculty of Veterinary Medicine	154	19%
2. Faculty of Tourism & Hotels	93	12%
3. Genetic Engineering Research Institute	124	16%
4. Faculty of Physical Education	186	23%
5. Faculty of Education	49	6%
6. Faculty of Commerce	69	9%
7. Faculty of Law	59	7%
8. Institute for Environmental Studies and Research	50	6%
9. Faculty of Pharmacy	17	2%
Total	801	100%

Source: Staff Members Affairs Department, Sadat University, Egypt, 2019

Descriptive statistics are used to describe some of the features of the respondents at SCU in Egypt who participated in the survey.

Table (2) Frequency Distribution Table of Demographics

Research Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Gender	Male	155	49%
	Female	160	51%
	Total	315	100%
2- The Academic Degree	Professor degree	50	16%
	Associate professor	75	24%
	Assistant professor	100	32%
	Lecturer	35	11%
	Demonstrator	55	17%
	Total	315	100%
3- Marital Status	Married	225	71%
	Single	90	29%
	Total	315	100%
4- Age	Less than 30 years	45	14%
	From 30 to 45	150	48%
	More than 45	120	38%
	Total	315	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	150	48%
	From 5 to 10	100	32%
	More than 10	65	20%
	Total	315	100%

7. The Survey Structure

The survey used to measure PL, JS and OC at SCU. This survey consists of three parts. The first described the objectives of the research by asking the respondents to participate in the survey. The second asked for the respondents' demographic variables such as gender, academic degree, marital status, age, and period of experience. The third presented the questions related to PL, JS and OC at SCU. About 400 questionnaires were distributed. 315 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 79%.

8. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 15-item scale of PL is based on Rajasekar & Beh, 2013; Kai, 2013; Fu, et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2012; Cheng, 2009. There were five items measuring benevolent leadership, five items measuring moral leadership, and five items measuring authoritarian leadership. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at SCU in Egypt.

The 10-item scale of JS is based on Judge et al., 2001; and Best & Thurston, 2004. There were five items measuring internal satisfaction and five items measuring external satisfaction. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at SCU in Egypt.

The 18-item scale of OC is based on Allan & Meyer, 1990; Meyer, et. al., 1993. There were six items measuring affective commitment, six items measuring continuance commitment, and six items measuring normative commitment. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure OC at SCU in Egypt. Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement which ranges from (5) "full agreement," (4) for "agree," (3) for "neutral," (2) for "disagree," and (1) for "full disagreement".

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

9.1. Coding of Variables

The research consists of two main variables. The first is PL (independent variable). The second is JA (dependent variable). Each variable consists of sub-variables. The main variables, sub-variables, number of the statement, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3): Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables		Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	PL	Benevolent Leadership	5	Rajasekar & Beh, 2013; Kai, 2013; Fu, et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2012
		Moral Leadership	5	
		Authoritarian Leadership	5	
		Total	15	
Dependent Variable	JS	Internal Satisfaction	5	Judge et al., 2001; Best & Thurston, 2004
		External Satisfaction	5	
		Total	10	
	OC	Affective Commitment	6	Allan & Meyer, 1990; Meyer, et. al., 1993
		Continuance Commitment	6	
		Normative Commitment	6	
		Total	16	

9.2. Descriptive Analysis

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out means and standard deviations of PL, JS, and OC.

Table (4): shows the mean and standard deviations of PL, JS and OC

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
PL	Benevolent Leadership	3.25	1.12
	Moral Leadership	3.17	0.939
	Authoritarian Leadership	2.87	1.06
	Total Measurement	3.10	0.764
JS	Internal Satisfaction	3.74	1.22
	External Satisfaction	3.67	1.32
	Total Measurement	3.71	1.25
OC	Affective Commitment	3.59	0.903
	Continuance Commitment	3.43	1.071
	Normative Commitment	3.59	1.047
	Total Measurement	2.65	0.708

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (4), presented the various facets of PL, JS and OC. Most of the respondents identified the presence of PL (M=3.10, SD=0.764), JS (M=3.71, SD=1.25) and OC (M=2.65, SD=0.708).

9.3. Evaluating Reliability

Data analysis was conducted. All scales were first subjected to reliability analysis. ACC was used to assess the reliability of the scales. Item analysis indicated that dropping any item from the scales would not significantly raise the alphas.

Table (5): Reliability of PL, JS and OC

Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
PL	Benevolent Leadership	5	0.874
	Moral Leadership	5	0.719
	Authoritarian Leadership	5	0.803
	Total Measurement	15	0.834
JS	Internal Satisfaction	5	0.966
	External Satisfaction	5	0.960
	Total Measurement	10	0.979
OC	Affective Commitment	6	0.905
	Continuance Commitment	6	0.941
	Normative Commitment	6	0.908
	Total Measurement	18	0.964

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (5) presents the reliability of PL, JS and OC. The 15-items of PL are reliable because the ACC is 0.834. The 10-items of JS is reliable because the ACC is 0.979. The 18-items of OC is reliable because the ACC is 0.964. Thus, the internal consistency of PL, JS and OC can be acceptable.

9.4. The Means, St. Deviations and Correlation among Variables

Table (6): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	PL	JS	OC
PL	3.10	0.764	1		
JS	3.71	1.25	0.270**	1	
OC	2.65	0.708	- 0.470**	- 0.381**	1

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Regarding Table (6), the level of PL is high (Mean=3.10; SD=0.764), while JS is (Mean=3.71; SD=1.25), and OC is (Mean=2.65; SD=0.708).The correlation between PL and JS is 0.270. Also, the correlation between PL and OC is 0.470.

9.5. The Correlation between PL and JS

The relationship between PL and JS at SCU in Egypt is presented in the following table:

Table (7) Correlation Matrix between PL and JS

Research Variables	1	2	3	4
Benevolent Leadership	1			
Moral Leadership	0.863**	1		
Authoritarian Leadership	0.031**	0.026**	1	
Job Satisfaction	0.388**	0.421**	0.200**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), the correlation between PL (benevolent leadership) and JS is 0.388. For PL (moral leadership) and JS, the value is 0.421 whereas PL (authoritarian leadership) and JS show a correlation value of 0.200. The overall correlation between PL and JS is 0.270.

9.5.1. Paternalistic Leadership (Benevolent Leadership) and JS

The relationship between PL (Benevolent Leadership) and JS is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no statistically significant relationship between PL (Benevolent Leadership) and JS at SCU in Egypt.

Table (8) MRA Results for PL (Benevolent Leadership) and JS

The Variables of PL (Benevolent Leadership)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss often cares and worries about the lives of his subordinates.	0.176	0.337	0.113
2. My boss often inquires about my health and living conditions in everyday life.	0.051	0.301	0.090
3. My boss gives me helping when I have trouble to reduce work pressure.	0.298**	0.222	0.049
4. My boss often provides care for my family and me as if we were his sons.	0.294**	0.317	0.100
5. My boss often seeks any well-being of subordinates.	0.278**	0.395	0.156
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.460	
		0.211	
		16.568	
		5, 309	
		3.01	
		0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.460 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of PL (Benevolent Leadership) construe JS significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of PL (Benevolent Leadership) can explain 0.21% of the total factors at the JS level. Hence, 79% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.5.2. Paternalistic Leadership (Moral Leadership) and JS

The relationship between PL (Moral Leadership) and JS is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: PL (Moral Leadership) of employees has no statistically significant effect on JS at SCU in Egypt.

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0. 0.434. This means that JS has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of PL (Moral Leadership). As a result of the value of R², the five independent variables of PL (Moral Leadership) justified only 18% of the total factors at the JS level. Hence, 82% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (9) MRA Results for PL (Moral Leadership) and JS

The Variables of PL (Moral Leadership)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss enjoys credibility and integrity at work.	0.059	0.188	0.035
2. My boss treats subordinates impartially at work.	0.091	0.332	0.110
3. My boss offers the interest of subordinates on his own interests.	0.101*	0.204	0.041
4. My boss is a good example for subordinates.	0.070	0.317	0.100
5. My boss is concerned with the specialization and professional controls at work.	0.262**	0.395	0.156
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.434	
		0.188	
		14.308	
		5, 309	
		3.01	
		0.000	

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

9.5.3. Paternalistic Leadership (Authoritarian Leadership) and JS

The relationship between PL (Authoritarian Leadership) and JS is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between PL (Authoritarian Leadership) and JS at SCU in Egypt.

Table (10) MRA Results for PL (Authoritarian Leadership) and JS

The Variables of PL (Authoritarian Leadership)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss is not transparent at work.	0.161	0.109	0.011
2. My boss makes management decisions independently.	0.060	0.044	0.001
3. My boss brings a lot of pressure when I work with him.	- 0.007	0.137	0.018
4. My boss reprimands if he does not do his job.	- 0.199**	0.218	0.047
5. My boss shall be made the final decision to work independently.	- 0.278**	0.222	0.049
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.293 0.086 5.812 5, 309 3.01 0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.293 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of PL (Authoritarian Leadership) construe JS significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of PL (Authoritarian Leadership) can explain 0.8% of the total factors at the JS level. Hence, 92% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.6. The Correlation between PL and OC

The relationship between PL and OC at SCU in Egypt is presented in the following table:

Table (11) Correlation Matrix between PL and OC

Research Variables	1	2	3	4
Benevolent Leadership	1			
Moral Leadership	0.863**	1		
Authoritarian Leadership	0.031**	0.026**	1	
Organizational Commitment	0.481**	0.578**	0.058**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (11), the correlation between PL (benevolent leadership) and OC is 0.481. For PL (moral leadership) and OC, the value is 0.578 whereas PL (authoritarian leadership) and OC show a correlation value of 0.058. The overall correlation between PL and OC is 0.470.

9.6.1. Paternalistic Leadership (Benevolent Leadership) and OC

The relationship between PL (Benevolent Leadership) and OC is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

H4: There is no statistically significant relationship between PL (Benevolent Leadership) and OC at SCU in Egypt.

Table (12) MRA Results for PL (Benevolent Leadership) and OC

The Variables of PL (Benevolent Leadership)	Beta	R	R ²
1. How many different direct customers you have across all operations and business units?	0.831**	0.123	0.015
2. How many products and services do you supply?	- 0.494**	0.162	0.026
3. How many different suppliers do you have?	- 0.112**	0.413	0.170
4. How many countries do you operate in?	- 0.401**	0.463	0.214
5. How many industries do you conduct business in?	- 0.434**	0.537	0.288
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.666 0.443 49.177 5, 309 3.01 0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.666 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of PL (Benevolent Leadership) construe OC significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of PL (Benevolent Leadership) can explain 0.44% of the total factors in OC level. Hence, 56% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.6.2. Paternalistic Leadership (Moral Leadership) and OC

The relationship between PL (Moral Leadership) and OC is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

H5: PL (moral leadership) of employees has no statistically significant effect on OC at SCU in Egypt.

Table (13) MRA Results for PL (Moral Leadership) and OC

The Variables of PL (Moral Leadership)	Beta	R	R ²
1. To what degree decisions require input from multiple business units within the company?	- 0.242**	0.435	0.189
2. To what extent does your organization use matrix structures, which force employees to respond	0.058	0.318	0.101
3. To what extent do senior managers in your company have multiple reporting lines?	- 0.111**	0.202	0.040
4. To what extent does your company have multiple dimensions of equal importance at the top	- 0.197**	0.463	0.214
5. To what extent does your company have multiple dimensions of equal importance at the top	- 0.348**	0.537	0.288
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.622 0.387 39.050 5, 309 3.01 0.000	

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (13) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.622 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of PL (Moral Leadership) construe OC significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of PL (Moral Leadership) can explain 0.38% of the total factors in OC level. Hence, 62% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.6.3. Paternalistic Leadership (Authoritarian Leadership) and OC

The relationship between PL (Authoritarian Leadership) and OC is determined. The sixth hypothesis to be tested is:

H6: There is no relationship between PL (authoritarian leadership) and OC at SCU in Egypt.

As Table (14) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.205 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of PL (Authoritarian Leadership) construe OC significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of PL (Authoritarian Leadership) can explain 0.4% of the total factors in OC level. Hence, 96% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (14) MRA Results for OM (Authoritarian Leadership) and OC

The Variables of PL (Authoritarian Leadership)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Management processes are inefficient, unclear, and require more info.	- 0.083	0.040	0.001
2. Operating processes are inefficient, unclear, and	- 0.157*	0.172	0.029
3. The company is not very integrated. Systems and processes are not interlinked, use different data	- 0.005	0.005	0.002
4. The IT systems are ineffective; they are overly complex and do not keep pace with the company	- 0.032	0.083	0.006
5. The IT systems are ineffective; they are overly complex and do not keep pace with the company	0.172*	0.051	0.002
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.205 0.042 2.701 5, 309 3.01 0.000	

** P < .01

10. Research Results

1. The current research has shown that the dimensions of Paternalistic Leadership (benevolent leadership, moral leadership, and authoritarian leadership) play an important role in influencing the job attitudes of employees at SCU.
2. SCU suffers from the widespread phenomenon of the leader's adherence to work-related information and not disclosing it to subordinates, which leads to dissatisfaction with its employees.
3. The leader at SCU cares about the subordinates and takes care of the amount of work they do, but does not care about their social matters.
4. The current research indicates that after (benevolent leadership) was ranked first with an average (3.25), moral leadership came in second place with an average (3.17), and authoritarian leadership came in third place with an average (2.87). However, benevolent leadership plays an important role in achieving employee satisfaction and hence greatly influencing their behavior and achieving the objectives of SCU.
5. The leader of SCU is credible and honest, but does not offer the interests of subordinates on his own reconciliation. They work to resolve differences between individuals by encouraging cooperation and informally.
6. The leader of SCU does not provide assistance to those who are absent from work or make recommendations for the development of the university.
7. The leader of SCU is characterized by not participating in decision-making with subordinates and insisting on his opinion.
8. The staff of SCU suffer from the leader's perverted behaviors that negatively affect them, and thus their performance.
9. Some employees of SCU feel that they are from the same family and have more intimate relationships than work relations, which increases their morale and strengthens their trust and makes them more connected to the university.
10. The leader's interest in employees at SCU and his pursuit of their goals motivates them to do more to provide the best possible for the university. This increases positive behaviors and reduces deviant behaviors at the university.

11. Recommendations

1. Leaders at SCU should engage subordinates in decision-making and allow them to express their opinions and suggestions. In other words, the need to pay attention to the participation of workers in SCU in decision-making because of its impact on the quality of work life within the university.
2. Leaders in SCU should follow a differentiated behavior that is appropriate to each circumstance or situation to minimize or reduce the deviant behavior.
3. Exerting pressure on subordinates at SCU and dealing with them severely generates adverse side effects that affect their job performance.
4. It is developing a set of regulations and laws that determine the competencies and powers of managers and staff at SCU in order to avoid tyrannical leadership because of its negative impact on work within the university.
5. Making the employees identical with SCU by adopting different means including generating a sense of being part of the university and involving it in decision-making. Ensuring the availability of justice in all its aspects, which contributes significantly to reducing the deviant behavior.
6. Leaders at SCU should do more to improve positive staff behaviors and reduce deviant behaviors. This has a positive impact on organizational outputs and the reputation of the university.
7. It is providing the principle of democracy in dealing with employees at SCU with the necessity of the director of ethical aspects when dealing with his subordinates because of its moral impact within the work at the University.
8. Leaders at SCU should put restrictions on the practice of negative behaviors by activating a strict control system as well as applying strict rules towards those who do these behaviors.
9. Leaders at SCU should increase the awareness of individuals of the importance of the role they play, through the freedom to express their views and suggestions.

10. The need to provide justice among workers, whether fair in the procedures justice (the existence of declared rules for all subordinates with powers and competencies, as well as distributive justice (fair wages among workers of the same job grade, especially in the dealings justice (not favoring one of the workers at the expense of another) at SCU.
11. The administration of SCU and all higher education institutions should urge their researchers to study the causes that lead to the spread of deviant behavior and the means of reducing it. This behavior has become widespread in most organizations, both in the public and private sectors.
12. Leaders at SCU should set an example for others, and follow the best means to win staff and take care of their interests.
13. Leaders at SCU should balance the interests of subordinates with their own and not favor their own interests over those of others.
14. Leaders at SCU should work to raise the level of awareness of staff towards the importance of cooperation among them, and work in a team spirit, which contributes to achieving the objectives of the university.
15. Leaders at SCU should listen to the complaints of staff and deal with them impartially and do not differentiate among them, which increases their respect for their leaders.
16. The existence of deviant behaviors in SCU is clear evidence of the adoption of false methods in the management of the university. This negatively affects the productivity of its employees. Thus, its impact on the conduct of the educational process in general, and on the colleges affiliated to the university, in particular is negative.

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